

1 Teleconnection-based evaluation of seasonal forecast 2 quality

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7 **Abstract** In response to the high demand for more skillful climate forecasts at the
8 seasonal timescale, innovative climate prediction systems are developed with im-
9 proved physics and increased spatial resolution. Alongside the model development
10 process, seasonal predictions need to be evaluated on past years to provide robust
11 information on the forecast performance. This work presents the quality assessment
12 of the Météo-France coupled climate prediction system, taking advantage of an ex-
13 periment performed with 90 ensemble members over a 37-year re-forecast period
14 from 1979 to 2015. We focus on the boreal winter season initialised in November.
15 Beyond typical skill measures we evaluate the model capability in reproducing
16 ENSO and NAO teleconnections on precipitation and near surface temperature
17 respectively. Such an assessment is carried out first through a composite analy-
18 sis, and shows that the model succeeds in reproducing the main patterns for near
19 surface temperature and precipitation. A covariance method leads to consistent
20 results. Finally we find that the teleconnection representation of the model is not
21 affected by shortening the verification period and reducing the ensemble size and
22 therefore can be used to evaluate operational seasonal forecast systems.

23 **Keywords** seasonal climate prediction · teleconnection · ENSO · NAO

24 1 Introduction

25 Seasonal predictions provide climate information for timescales ranging from one
26 month to one year. Several studies have proven that state-of-the-art coupled cli-
27 mate models are able to produce skillful extra-tropical predictions at such time
28 scales (e.g. Riddle et al., 2013; Scaife et al., 2014; Kang et al., 2014; Dunstone
29 et al., 2016). The sources of seasonal predictability rely upon the existence of slow

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30 components of the natural climate variability, associated with variations of soil
31 moisture, snow cover, sea-ice, and ocean surface temperature (Doblas-Reyes et al.,
32 2013; Smith et al., 2012). El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) is the main pro-
33 cess that contributes to the forecast quality in the Tropics (Scaife et al., 2017), as
34 well as in large parts of the world, due to its expanded remote impacts (Shaman,
35 2014). Teleconnections with the Tropics and the Arctic (Jung et al., 2016), as well
36 as variations in soil moisture and snow (Douville, 2010), also contribute to cli-
37 mate predictability over the extra-tropics. Seasonal predictability also arises from
38 the interactions between the troposphere associated with the tropospheric vortex
39 (Vaugh et al., 2017), and the stratosphere associated with the quasi-biennial oscil-
40 lation (Marshall and Scaife, 2009). Over Europe, seasonal climate is also influenced
41 by the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) (Hurrell and van Loon, 1997).

42 ENSO and NAO are two important sources of variability at the seasonal time
43 scale. Several studies have investigated both their respective and combined effects
44 on climate, through observational or theoretical studies (Shaman, 2014; Mari-
45 otti et al., 2002; Rodó et al., 1997). Observational studies show that ENSO is
46 the largest source of predictability for the North Pacific, the North Atlantic, the
47 US precipitation and the Asian summer and winter monsoon (Ropelewski and
48 Halpert, 1987; Kumar et al., 2017). Numerous case studies have provided evidence
49 of ENSO effects also on temperature, sea level pressure and precipitation over
50 Europe (Brönnimann, 2007). The NAO is related with changes in regional precip-
51 itation and shifts in the storm track, as well as changes in the wave height, the
52 sea-ice extent and volume (Hurrell et al., 2003). Furthermore its strong positive
53 phase is associated with above-normal temperatures over eastern North America
54 and northern Europe, and below-normal temperatures in Greenland, southern Eu-
55 rope and the Middle East. Opposite conditions are typically observed during the
56 negative phase (van Loon and Rogers, 1978; Rogers and van Loon, 1979).

57 As for the prediction of the respective indices, different aspects need to be consid-
58 ered. On the one hand, there is the evaluation of the prediction skill, which in the
59 seasonal to decadal prediction community is typically measured with the Pearson
60 correlation coefficient calculated over a sample of the past years forecasts and the
61 corresponding observations (e.g. Goddard et al. (2013)). This deterministic mea-
62 sure investigates the linear correspondence between forecast and reference dataset
63 in time and, as any verification measure, needs a quantification of the associated
64 uncertainty (Siegert et al., 2017).

65 In addition to the influence of model biases on seasonal prediction skill, there
66 are three sources of uncertainty that compromise the reliability of common scor-
67 ing metrics, namely the small-sized ensembles, the insufficient number of forecast
68 cases and the imperfect reference values, due to observation uncertainties (Doblas-
69 Reyes et al., 2003; Siegert et al., 2016). A proper evaluation of the prediction skill
70 of a system would therefore require the use of several metrics combined with a
71 long verification period. For the re-forecasts, going too far back with the aim of
72 extending the number of years of verification is at the cost of losing accuracy in
73 the initial conditions, and therefore degrading the levels of skill.

74 In this study we focus on ENSO and NAO variability modes. While ENSO is
75 recognised as the predominant source of predictability (Anderson et al., 1998),
76 prediction of the NAO at time-scales longer than a couple of weeks is now possible
77 (Butler et al., 2016). O'Reilly et al. (2017) as well as Weisheimer et al. (2017) have
78 recently suggested some variability in the NAO skill evaluations depending on the

hindcast period considered. Furthermore, a better NAO skill does not automatically mean an improvement in predicting its effects. Athanasiadis et al. (2017) shows with a multimodel ensemble with high NAO skill that depending on the area considered, Northern hemisphere temperature and precipitation skill can be improved with respect to model outputs using a regression onto the observed NAO pattern. This suggests that although the prediction skill of NAO is high, its teleconnections are not well represented in current dynamical forecasting systems. In fact, a separate issue to be addressed in the evaluation of a prediction is whether the model has a consistent response to the variability modes, capturing their impacts on other parts of the globe. A realistic representation of the teleconnection patterns is a key feature for a valuable forecast. This evaluation approach is also an attempt to address the need for a robust diagnostic that is not sensitive to the ensemble size and the length of the verification period, to assess the progress in model developments.

In this study we show how the use of a teleconnection-based diagnostic provides information on the seasonal forecast system which is robust because not sensitive to the ensemble size and the verification length, contrary to the skill score measures. We analyse the ENSO and NAO teleconnections with precipitation and near-surface temperature respectively, investigating tropical teleconnections with tropical index and extra-tropical teleconnection with extra-tropical index. Many studies have focused on the tropical/extra-tropical links: Cassou (2008) showed that the Madden Julian Oscillation highly affects the NAO distribution, Molteni et al. (2015) showed that reproducing the link between NAO and tropical rainfall is difficult at time scales ranging from intra-seasonal to the decadal. Deser et al. (2017) showed that the observed extra-tropical North hemisphere sea level pressure response to ENSO in boreal winter is subject to uncertainties in pattern and amplitude.

This study takes advantage of the long verification period (satellite era, 1979-2015) and the large ensemble size (90 members) of the experiment in use to study separately the response of the different phases of the variability modes through the composite analysis. Another approach to assess the teleconnection representation is the covariance method, which can be used with smaller ensemble size and shorter hindcast period, although there is the risk of a loss of information, due to the fact that the different phases of the variability modes are analysed together. Such a risk depends on the degree of symmetry of the responses of the different phases. We have therefore assessed this symmetry for each mode. The objective of our symmetry analysis is solely to evaluate the potential loss of information in the use of the covariance method. It should not be intended as an attempt to better characterize the variability modes, as done for example in Guo et al. (2017) for ENSO. We then repeat the study of teleconnections using the covariance method and assessing the consistency with the composite analysis results. Finally, we reduce the ensemble size and shorten the hindcast period to evaluate the representation of teleconnections on our typical (and operational) re-forecast size, which is also the standard required by the Copernicus Climate Change Services (C3S) framework. Section 2 describes the experiments and the methodology used in the paper. Section 3.1 presents the results of the composite analysis and the symmetry analysis, while section 3.2.1 shows the results of the covariance method and 3.2.2 assesses the effect of the ensemble size and the verification length. Finally the conclusions are drawn in section 4.

128 2 Experimental set up and methods

129 2.1 Datasets

130 The experiment evaluated in this work is based on the CNRM-CM global coupled
 131 model (Voldoire et al., 2013). It was run with ARPEGE-Climat version 6.2
 132 atmospheric component, where the atmospheric physics have been upgraded from
 133 the CMIP5 version (Gueremy, 2011). The resolution is T359 (0.5°) and 91 vertical
 134 levels with a vertical extent of approximately 81 Km. SURFEX v8 (Voldoire et al.,
 135 2017) is the land surface component with upgraded soil physics. The atmosphere
 136 and surface are coupled with 24 hour frequency through OASIS 3 (Valcke, 2013)
 137 to the ocean model NEMO version 3.2 (Madec, 2008) with 1° horizontal grid with
 138 42 vertical levels. The sea ice component is GELATO v6 directly embedded into
 139 NEMO (Salas y Melia, 2002). The retrospective forecasts analysed here are initial-
 140 ised on the 1st of November over the period 1979-2015 (37 years) with full
 141 field initialisation (Pohlmann et al., 2009) and are run for 4 forecast months. In
 142 this study we will therefore concentrate on the December-January-February season
 143 (DJF, forecast months 2, 3 and 4). The atmospheric component is initialised with
 144 ERA-Interim (Dee et al., 2011), while the ocean and sea-ice component are ini-
 145 tialised with ORA S4 (Alonso-Balmaseda et al., 2012). The 90 ensemble members
 146 are generated with stochastic perturbations in the atmosphere (Batte and Deque,
 147 2016).

148 The observed Nino3.4 SST index (N3.4) has been calculated with ERSST v4 data
 149 (Huang et al., 2015), while the NAO with the ERA-Interim data of geopotential
 150 height. Verification datasets are GPCP v2.3 (Adler et al., 2003) for precipitation
 151 and ERA-Interim for near surface temperature.

152 2.2 Methodology

153 To look at the performance of the model in forecasting El Nino 3.4 (hereafter
 154 referred to as N3.4) and the NAO we compute the Pearson correlation coefficient
 155 of the N3.4 and NAO indices, and the corresponding 95% confidence intervals
 156 calculated with a t-distribution. The dependence between the consecutive years is
 157 accounted for in the computation of the confidence interval using the Zwiers and
 158 von Storch (1995) formula.

159 As mentioned in section 1 we evaluate the capability of the model to represent
 160 the teleconnections of ENSO and NAO, respectively with precipitation and near
 161 surface temperature. To analyse the responses to the different phases of the modes
 162 we have used the composite analysis. Such an analysis provides an assessment of
 163 the patterns associated to each mode in the model, independent of the forecast
 164 skill.

165 The following steps have been implemented to compute the composite of the index
 166 of interest I (N3.4 or NAO) and a variable of the system $f(g)$ (precipitation and
 167 temperature respectively, g being the spatial coordinates):

- 168 – One seasonal value for the index I has been calculated for each of the 37 years
 169 available. N3.4 has been calculated as the temperature area average over the
 170 Nino 3.4 region (Trenberth, 1997), 120°W - 170°W and 5°S - 5°N . The NAO

index has been calculated as the leading EOF of geopotential height anomalies at 500 hPa over the North Atlantic region (20°N-80°N, 80°W-40°E). The principal components are obtained by projecting the forecast and observed anomalies onto the observed EOF pattern.

- The 37 values of the index I have been divided into three categories, choosing between the 12 years with the lowest values, the 12 with the highest values, and leaving 13 years in the intermediate category. These three categories for I are defined by two thresholds T_1 and T_2 , that correspond approximately to the terciles.
- The partition of years according to categories for index I is then applied to the variable $f(g)$.
- The composite between the index and the variable $f(g)$ is then calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} x^+ &= \sum_{y=1}^{years} \frac{\mathbb{1}(I_y > T_2) \cdot f_y(g)}{\sum_{y=1}^{years} \mathbb{1}(I_y > T_2)} - \sum_{y=1}^{years} \frac{\mathbb{1}(T_1 < I_y < T_2) \cdot f_y(g)}{\sum_{y=1}^{years} \mathbb{1}(T_1 < I_y < T_2)} \\ x^- &= \sum_{y=1}^{years} \frac{\mathbb{1}(I_y < T_1) \cdot f_y(g)}{\sum_{y=1}^{years} \mathbb{1}(I_y < T_1)} - \sum_{y=1}^{years} \frac{\mathbb{1}(T_1 < I_y < T_2) \cdot f_y(g)}{\sum_{y=1}^{years} \mathbb{1}(T_1 < I_y < T_2)} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbb{1}(I_y > T_2)$ is the Heaviside function that takes the value of 1 if $I_y > T_2$ or 0 otherwise. As indicated in equation 1 x^+ is the difference between the positive and the neutral composites. Analogously x^- is the difference between the negative and the neutral composites. This has been calculated for both the model and the reference data. For the model, each member has been treated separately, which means having available 90 times the number of the seasons of the observations.

To measure the symmetry of the phase responses we used the following metric:

$$sym = 1 - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\|x^+ + x^-\|^2}{\|x^+\|^2 + \|x^-\|^2} \quad (2)$$

where $\| \cdot \|$ indicates the weighted Euclidean norm. The index sym compares the antisymmetric component $\|x^+ + x^-\|^2$ with the total variance $\|x^+\|^2 + \|x^-\|^2$. It is limited between 0 and 1, with 1 indicating a fully symmetric response (when $x^+ = -x^-$), and 0 indicating a complete antisymmetric response (when $x^+ = x^-$). In section 3.2.1 we look at teleconnections through the covariances as in Guérémy et al. (2005), after verifying the degree of symmetry between the phases of the modes. The covariance is calculated as the sum of the product between the standardized index $< I_y >$ and the variable $f_y(g)$:

$$C(g) = \frac{\sum_{y=1}^{years} < I_y > \cdot f_y(g)}{years} \quad (3)$$

Finally we assess the impact of the verification length and the ensemble size, by comparing the pattern correlation between the model and reference covariances when using a shorter verification period and a smaller ensemble size.

3 Results

3.1 Composite

Over 1979-2015, the Pearson correlation coefficient of DJF N3.4 with respect to ERSST data is 0.98 with a 95% confidence interval between 0.95 and 0.99. Figure 1 shows the composite of N3.4 and precipitation calculated as in equation 1. The top row represents the model 90 members composites average, while the bottom row shows the composites in the reference data. The model patterns are generally shifted westward. The strongest amplitude of the signal is in the Tropical Pacific during the positive phase (left column). During both phases the model succeeds in capturing the tripole of the Pacific Tropical band, as well as the signal in the Tropical Atlantic, although the amplitude of the signal is weaker, especially in the areas where the reference data shows the strongest anomalies. Over land, the modeled signal is consistent with observations over Indonesia and Philippines but the observed signal is missed over inland Australia. In South Africa and South America the model reproduces the pattern of the positive phase (panel a), but the signal is not captured during the negative phase (panel b). The model also fails to capture the signal on the East Atlantic in the northern hemisphere during the negative phase. Also N3.4 teleconnections with near surface temperature and 500 *hPa* geopotential height is well represented by the model (not shown).

The Pearson correlation of the NAO model index for DJF with respect to ERA-Interim is 0.42 with a 95% confidence interval between 0.11 and 0.65. Even if the skill score has a high level of uncertainty, the teleconnection with near surface temperature is generally well captured (Figure 2). As for the precipitation composite with N3.4, the intensity of the model signal is often weaker than observed, although it is geographically well placed: the maximum in temperature over Russia during NAO⁺ (panel a), and the minimum over Greenland and Canada, as well as the minimum over Russia during NAO⁻ (panel b) and the maximum over Greenland and Canada are well captured. There is an observed maximum over Canada during NAO⁺ (panel c) which is not reproduced in the model (panel a), and a maximum in the Bering Strait during NAO⁻ (panel d), which is restricted to Alaska in the model (panel b).

As mentioned in the introduction the ultimate scope of such an analysis is the evaluation of operational seasonal forecasts with a smaller ensemble size and a shorter verification period. The next step of this study is therefore to verify that the analysis of the combined effect of the variability mode phases together through the covariance method does not imply a major loss of information. The metric presented in equation 2 is an arbitrary index to measure the symmetry of the response in terms of sign of the teleconnection, and to compare the model behaviour with reality in terms of the degree of symmetry. A symmetric response of the variability mode phases ensures a limited loss of information when evaluating the mode phases together. This is of interest in the study of teleconnections especially when a long verification period is not available, since further separating the data into phases would lead to too small samples and high levels of uncertainty. For the model, the metric *sym* has been calculated computing the metric for the composites of each member and then averaging the 90 *sym* values.

Fig. 1. Composite of N3.4 and precipitation for DJF calculated as described in equation 1. The left column shows the difference between the positive and the neutral condition, while the right column is the difference between the negative and the neutral condition. The model composites are shown in panel a and b, while the observation in panel c and d: the N3.4 index is computed with ERSST data, while for precipitation GPCP v2.3 dataset is used. The solid and dashed contours indicate respectively the positive and negative values.

Domains	Reference	Model members	5%-95% percentiles of the members
North	0.51	0.39	0.28-0.53
Tropic	0.52	0.38	0.31-0.45
Atlantic domain (60°W-20°E)	0.55	0.51	0.40-0.63
Indian domain (21°E-100°E)	0.46	0.49	0.41-0.58
Pacific domain (101°E-61°W)	0.74	0.68	0.64-0.72
South	0.72	0.67	0.63-0.70

Table I. Measure of the symmetry (*sym*) of the N3.4 and precipitation composites. The first column shows the reference data *sym* values. In the second column *sym* is calculated for each model member composite before averaging over the 90 members and the third column indicates the 90% interval of the member *sym* values. The rows indicate the geographical domains: North band (between 90°N-31°N), Tropical band (between 30°N-30°S) which has also been split in different basins (Atlantic 60°W-20°E, Indian 21°E-100°E and Pacific 101°E-61°W), and South band (between 31°S-90°S).

Fig. 2. Composite of NAO and near surface temperature for DJF calculated as described in equation 1. The left column shows the difference between NAO^+ phase and the neutral condition, while the right column is the difference between the NAO^- phase and the neutral condition. The model composites are shown in panel a and b, while the reference data in panel c and d. ERA-Interim reanalysis is used for both the calculation of NAO and the near surface temperature reference. The solid and dashed contours indicate respectively the positive and negative values.

248 Table I shows the values of *sym* for the precipitation composites with N3.4, di-
 249 vided into latitudinal domains: North (31°N - 90°N), Tropic (30°N - 30°S) and South
 250 (31°S - 90°S). The tropical band has been divided into longitudinal domains which
 251 we refer to as Atlantic (60°W - 20°E), Indian (21°E - 100°E) and Pacific (101°E -
 252 61°W). Note that they do not correspond to the ocean basins, but to the regions
 253 (with land included). The first column lists the metric of the reference data, while
 254 the second and third columns show respectively the average metric of the model
 255 members, and the 90% interval of the members. The *sym* values of the reference
 256 data and the model members (first and second column) are comparable and the
 257 values of the reference index stay in the confidence interval of the model mem-
 258 bers (third column). Therefore model and reference data have a similar degree
 259 of symmetry. Analogous results are found for the *sym* values of the temperature
 260 composites with NAO over the 30°N - 90°N region shown in Table II.

	Reference	Model members	5%-95% percentiles of the members
Sym	0.68	0.62	0.44-0.77

Table II. Measure of the symmetry (sym) of the NAO and near surface temperature composites over the 30°N 90°N region. The first column shows the reference data sym values. In the second column sym is calculated for each model member composite and the third column indicates the 90% interval of the members.

261 Note that the index sym in Table I quantifies the variability of ENSO limited
 262 in the specific region N3.4 described in section 2. Frauen et al. (2014) studied
 263 the issue of the difference in ENSO phase responses both in terms of amplitude
 264 and symmetry of the signal. They found a stronger signal during El Niño events
 265 (consistently with what is shown in Figure 1), but they found no symmetry in the
 266 sign of the response. This discrepancy of results could be due to the sensitivity to
 267 the definition of ENSO and the fact that they use two different spatial patterns
 268 to define El Niño and La Niña events.
 269 However following the definition of the indices described in section 2, our results
 270 suggest that the loss of information when evaluating the mode phases together is
 271 limited, and therefore encourage us to use the covariance method.

272 3.2 Covariances

273 3.2.1 Consistency with the composites results

274 The model and observed covariances between N3.4 and precipitation (Figure 3)
 275 show consistent results with what was found with the composite analysis. The
 276 pattern shown is very similar to the composite during the positive phase (Figure
 277 1a and 1c), due to the fact that the signal of the positive phase of N3.4 has a
 278 stronger amplitude than the negative phase. In order to quantify such a similarity
 279 Table III lists the pattern correlation between the positive phase composite and
 280 the covariance (i.e. between Figure 1a and 3a for the model, and 1c and 3b for
 281 the reference data) for the domains defined in Table I. The pattern correlation
 282 values confirm the consistency between the covariance patterns and the composite
 283 analysis during N3.4 positive phase. The model overestimates the correspondence
 284 in all domains. This confirms that the response to N3.4 is more linear in the model
 285 than in observation.
 286

Fig. 3. Covariance of N3.4 and precipitation for DJF calculated as described in equation 3. Covariances are shown for the model in panel a, and for the reference data in panel b: the N3.4 index is computed with ERSST data, while for precipitation GPCP v2.3 dataset is used. The verification period is 37 years (1979-2015). The solid and dashed contours indicate respectively the positive and negative values.

Domains	Model	Reference
Atlantic domain (60°W-20°E)	0.97	0.87
Indian domain (21°E-100°E)	0.96	0.77
Pacific domain (101°E-61°W)	0.95	0.93

Table III. Pattern correlation between the covariance and the composite analysis of the positive phase of N3.4 in the tropical region 30°N-30°S. The pattern correlation is calculated separately for model (first column), and the reference data (second column, ERSST data for the computation of N3.4 and GPCP v2.3 dataset for the precipitation). The rows represent the different domains of the tropical band: Atlantic 60°W-20°E, Indian 21°E-100°E and Pacific 101°E-61°W.

287 In order to compare the signal amplitude between model and observation, Fig-
 288 ure 4 shows the root mean square covariances of the ensemble members of the
 289 experiment (interquartile range in red, median in black) and the observation (in
 290 blue) averaged for some regions selected from the area of observed covariance
 291 signal: Southern Africa (SAFR, 35°S-12°S, 10°W-52°E), Southeast Asia (SEA,
 292 11°S-20°N, 95°E-155°E) and Northeast Brazil (EBR, 10°S-10°N, 30°W-70°W)¹.
 293 In all regions the ensemble spans the observed value and for the SAFR and EBR
 294 regions the interquartile range of the members show a weaker amplitude than the
 295 observed values. The study of the pattern correlation between model and observed
 296 covariances is shown in the following subsection.

297

Fig. 4. Box plot of the root mean square model ensemble member covariances between N3.4 and precipitation averaged over specific regions. The red boxes indicate the interquartile range of the members for the model in each region. The median of the ensemble members is plotted in black. The observed root mean square covariances (calculated with GPCP v2.3 dataset for precipitation and ERSST data for the computation of N3.4) regional averages are showed in blue. The regions are defined as follows: Southern Africa (SAFR, 35°S-12°S, 10°W-52°E), Southeast Asia (SEA, 11°S-20°N, 95°E-155°E) and Northeast Brazil (EBR, 10°S-10°N, 30°W-70°W)

298 The model is able to well capture the NAO teleconnection with temperature (Fig-
 299 ure 5) although the signal is weaker than the observation. This is consistent with
 300 past results from Scaife et al. (2014) with another seasonal forecast system.
 301 Analogously to what happens for N3.4, the covariances of temperature with NAO
 302 show a similar pattern to the signal shown in the NAO positive phase composite
 303 (Figure 2 a and 2 c) for both the model and the observation. The correspon-
 304 dence between the model positive composite and the covariance is higher (pattern
 305 correlation of 0.98) than for the reference data (pattern correlation 0.75).

¹ The first two domains, SAFR and SEA are selected following the geographical definition of Giorgi and Francisco (2000), while the last domain EBR is chosen selecting an area with observed signal of N3.4 over precipitation.

Fig. 5. Covariance of NAO and near surface temperature for DJF calculated as described in equation 3 with 37-years verification period (1979-2015). Covariances are shown for the model in panel a, and for the reference data (ERA-Interim reanalysis) in panel b. The solid and dashed contours indicate respectively the positive and negative values.

Fig. 6. Box plot of the root mean square model ensemble member covariances between NAO and near surface temperature averaged over specific regions. The red boxes indicate the interquartile range of the members for the model in each region. The median of the ensemble members is plotted in black. The reference root mean square covariances (calculated with ERA-Interim reanalysis) regional averages are shown in blue. The regions are defined as follows: Mediterranean (MED, 30°N-48°N, 10°W-40°E), eastern North America (ENA, 25°N-50°N, 85°W-60°W) and Northern Europe (NEU, 48°N-75°N, 10°W-40°E).

306 Figure 6 shows the root mean square of the ensemble members covariances of
 307 the experiments averaged for the following domains: eastern North America (ENA,
 308 25°N-50°N, 85°W-60°W) Northern Europe (NEU, 48°N-75°N, 10°W-40°E) and
 309 Mediterranean (MED, 30°N-48°N, 10°W-40°E), chosen for the known potential
 310 impacts of winter NAO on the climate of the region (Rojas et al., 2013; López-

311 Moreno et al., 2011). The model ensemble spans the observed values in all regions
 312 and while for the MED and NEU regions the 75% of the members have a weaker
 313 signal than the observed, for ENA the median of the members is very close to the
 314 observed value.

315

316 3.2.2 Effect of the verification length

317 In order to mimic our standard operational experiment and investigate the effect
 318 of reducing the verification length and the ensemble size, we have reduced the
 319 hindcast period to 23 years, from 1993 to 2015, and we have divided the ensemble
 320 into three sets of 30 members. Figure 7 shows that no remarkable difference was
 321 found in the N3.4 and precipitation covariances when shortening the verification
 322 period (Figure 7 panel a is the covariance with 23 hindcast years, keeping the
 323 90-member ensemble), nor when reducing the ensemble size (panels b,d,e). This is
 324 consistent with the observational results, where no remarkable changes are noticed
 325 in the covariance calculated with a shortened verification period (Figure 7 panel
 326 c), compared with the covariance calculated with the 37-year verification period
 327 of Figure 3 panel b. To further reinforce these findings, we have calculated the
 328 pattern correlation between the model and the observed covariances in the tropical
 329 band where most of the signal is found, in order to seek for a point-by-point
 330 spatial correspondence. The first three columns of Table IV illustrates the pattern
 331 correlation of the covariance calculated with the three 30-member sets using the
 332 23-year verification period. The fourth column is the pattern correlation of the
 333 covariance for the shorter verification period, but all 90 members (corresponding
 334 to Figure 7 panel a), and the last column corresponds to the pattern correlation
 335 of the covariance for the 37-year verification period and the 90 ensemble members
 336 (corresponding to Figure 3). Independently of the basin considered, the pattern
 337 correlation shows no striking changes.

Domains	30 membs 23y	30 membs 23y	30 membs 23y	90 membs 23y	90 membs 37 y
Atlantic domain (60°W-20°E)	0.78	0.80	0.78	0.79	0.79
Indian domain (21°E-100°E)	0.64	0.69	0.65	0.67	0.66
Pacific domain (101°E-61°W)	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82

Table IV. Pattern correlation between the model and observed N3.4 and precipitation covariances in the tropical region 30°N-30°S. The pattern correlations of the first three columns are calculated respectively from the covariances of each of the model 30-member sets, with 23-year verification. The fourth column is the pattern correlation of the covariance calculated with 23-year verification and the model 90 members, and the last column correspond to the pattern correlation of the covariance calculated with the 37-year verification period and the 90 ensemble members. The rows represent the different domains of the tropical band: Atlantic 60°W-20°E, Indian 21°E-100°E and Pacific 101°E-61°W.

Fig. 7. Covariance of N3.4 and precipitation for DJF calculated as described in equation 3 with 23-years verification period (1993-2015). Covariances are shown for the model first considering the 90 members together (panel a), and then grouping them in 30-member sets (panels b,d and e). The reference data is shown in the panel c: the N3.4 index is computed with ERSST data, while for precipitation GPCP v2.3 dataset is used. The solid and dashed contours indicate respectively the positive and negative values.

338 With the shortening of the verification period the Pearson correlation of NAO
 339 appears higher (0.53 with a confidence interval between 0.15 and 0.77). However,
 340 when reducing the ensemble size to 30 members the Pearson correlation varies
 341 between 0.39 and 0.50, depending on the 30-member sets. Also Scaife et al. (2014)
 342 showed a clear ensemble size dependence of the NAO skill. On the other hand,
 343 the information extracted from the covariance study is less sensitive to the re-
 344 duction of verification years and ensemble members. In fact, when looking at the
 345 covariances between NAO and near surface temperature no remarkable changes
 346 are found for both the model and the reference data when the verification period
 347 is shortened to 23 years, nor when the ensemble size is reduced to 30 members
 348 (Figure 8). Table V lists the pattern correlations between model and observation
 349 for the different subsets. They vary between 0.88 (for one set of 30 members with
 350 a 23 year verification period) to 0.93 obtained with the full ensemble and the 37

351 hindcast years. These results suggest that while the study of the skill scores is
352 highly dependent to the ensemble size and the verification length, the study of
353 teleconnections is more robust because not sensitive to changes in ensemble size
354 and verification length.

Fig. 8. Covariance of NAO and near surface temperature for DJF calculated as described in equation 3 with 23-years verification period (1993-2015). Covariances are shown for the model first considering the 90 members together (panel a), and then grouping them in 30-member sets (panels b, d and e). The reference data is ERA-Interim reanalysis and is shown in panel c. The solid and dashed contours indicate respectively the positive and negative values.

30 membs 23y	30 membs 23y	30 membs 23y	90 membs 23y	90 membs 37 y
0.90	0.88	0.89	0.90	0.93

Table V. Pattern correlation of model and observed covariances of NAO with near surface temperature in the region 30°N-90°N. The pattern correlations of the first three columns are calculated respectively from the covariances of each of the model 30-member sets, with 23-year verification. The fourth column is the pattern correlation of the covariance calculated with 23-year verification and the model 90 members, and the last column correspond to the pattern correlation of the covariance calculated with the 37-year verification period and the 90 ensemble members.

355 4 Conclusions

356 In the verification of a seasonal climate prediction system there are three as-
 357 pects that are usually considered: the improvements in terms of systematic error,
 358 whether the discrepancy between the reference and modeled mean state is reduced,
 359 which might lead to forecast skill improvements (Ardilouze et al., 2019); the con-
 360 sistency in time, i.e. whether there is a time correspondence of the predicted and
 361 observed event, and whether the prediction has skill in the spatial representation
 362 of the event (spatial consistency). When it comes to comparing different hindcasts,
 363 for example to evaluate an upgraded forecast system after model developments,
 364 the use of the traditional skill scores often does not allow us to draw robust conclu-
 365 sions on whether the updated system is actually producing improved predictions.
 366 This happens because the skill maps are patchy, due to the short verification pe-
 367 riod and the limited ensemble size. This work takes its roots in the need for a
 368 robust evaluation to investigate the effects of model upgrades.

369 The diagnostic presented here is based on one specific fact: although the telecon-
 370 nection representation is not a measure of predictability, having a good connec-
 371 tivity is a necessary condition of a good prediction. In fact, we aim at predicting
 372 large temporal and spatial scale modes. However, having a high skill score for these
 373 modes is no guarantee to have a good prediction of their consequences. The added
 374 value of the study of the teleconnection related to the variability modes is that it
 375 provides information on the spatial consistency of the prediction.

376 In this study we have been focusing on Niño 3.4 (N3.4) and the NAO, because
 377 they are key phenomena that affect temperature and precipitation on large remote
 378 areas. They also have quite different levels of predictive skill, with ENSO being
 379 highly predictable, and NAO exhibiting a smaller variability on the seasonal scale,
 380 and with much more predictive uncertainty. We first used the composite analysis
 381 on a large 90-member ensemble experiment with a verification period of 37 years
 382 (from 1979 to 2015), to verify the robustness of the results. This method allowed
 383 us to look separately at each phase of the variability modes. In this work we have
 384 only shown the December-January-February season for November 1st initialisa-
 385 tion: as expected most of the N3.4 signal for precipitation is found in the tropical
 386 band and the positive phase records the strongest amplitude of the signal. The
 387 model successfully reproduces the N3.4 signal, as well as the NAO signal for near
 388 surface temperature, although the prediction skill of the index is lower.

389 Since the final targets of our diagnostic are operational seasonal forecast hindcasts
390 with a shorter verification period and a smaller ensemble size, we need a measure
391 of teleconnections that can be implemented even with our standard size hindcast,
392 which also corresponds to the C3S seasonal hindcast standards. The reduction
393 of the verification period would however imply the study of the modes phases
394 together, with the intrinsic risk of a loss of information. Therefore we measured
395 the symmetry of the mode phases responses to quantify the potential loss of in-
396 formation in the covariance method. We found that there is a reasonable level
397 of symmetry in sign of the variability modes responses for both the model and
398 the observational datasets. We then performed the teleconnection study using the
399 covariance method and we found consistent results with the composite analysis
400 study.

401 Successively we wanted to investigate the effect of using a shortened verification
402 period and a reduced ensemble size. We therefore selected the years from 1993 to
403 2015 (23 years verification period) and split the 90 ensemble members in three
404 sets of 30 members. We found that the use of our standard size hindcast does not
405 compromise the results in terms of covariance and corresponding pattern correla-
406 tion. These results support the idea that a conclusive way to evaluate operational
407 seasonal forecast systems is to integrate information coming from the skill scores
408 analysis, with the information extract from the study of teleconnections.

409 This study has been applied to one model (although some results confirm past
410 works with shorter and smaller ensembles). It would be interesting to have avail-
411 able such large and long ensemble re-forecasts with other models, in order to be
412 able to confirm these results with other seasonal forecast systems.

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420 ERA-Interim data are provided by the ECMWF, Reading, UK from their Web site at <http://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/>.
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